

Privacy Preservation in Textual Data: A Systematic Mapping Study on Differential Privacy and Semantic Similarity

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Table 1. SMS - Innovative Techniques

Novel Approaches	
Innovative Technique	Study
APDPk-means	[Fan and Xu 2019]
Enhanced Privacy and Data Protection using NLP and AI	[Martinelli et al. 2020]
Gan-Generated Speaker Embeddings	[Meyer et al. 2023]
Hashtag Graphbased Topic Model (HGTM)	[Wang et al. 2016]
Hierarchical Federated Collaborative Computing (HFCC)	[Han et al. 2025]
Improved Scalable k-Anonymization (ImSKA) using MapReduce	[Mehta et al. 2019]
Modified TF-IDF weighting scheme and Parallel Hybridization Approach (PHA)	[Al-Ghuribi et al. 2020]
Personalized Language Model Learning on Text Data Without User Identifiers	[Ding et al. 2025]
PromptFL - federated prompt training	[Guo et al. 2024]
Rx-Anon	[Singhofer et al. 2021]
s2v Vector Model	[Wang et al. 2018]
SEMCAT - New dataset	[enel et al. 2018]
Sentic LDA	[Poria et al. 2016]
SentiVec	[Zhu et al. 2021]
Semantic Weighted Context Tagging Engine	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Seeds Affinity Propagation (SAP)	[Guan et al. 2011]
SPEDAC	[Gambarelli et al. 2023]

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